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Intelligence community and private guard companies in Nigeria: The missing national security architecture links

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Abstract

The yawning loop between federal security agencies and the private security industries has an aggravating effects on the nonresponsiveness of the national security architecture, where almost all actors are siloed in a stand-alone-mode. As an interactive national security architecture fusing federal security agencies with private Guard Companies in Intelligence sharing networks, as seen in developed clime could have a catalytic effects on national security architecture. It was against this backdrop that this study leverages on participatory theory (Network Analysis Theory) to investigate the impact of intelligence community and private guard companies on national security architecture in Nigeria. The study deconstruct National Security into, economic security and education security. This study adopts qualitative research design using exploratory research design on publicly available archive documents; study also relies solely on secondary data. The research is conducted by examining literature concerning private security industry, national security architecture, intelligence community and its effects on human security in Nigeria. The literature was obtained through searches in publicly available material. Literature from non-serial publications, official reports, and conferences has been included particularly if they have been cited by other references in term of intelligence sharing and private Guard companies and effects on national security architecture. Results that originate from this study revealed that one of the effects of intelligence sharing between private security industry and government security agencies correlates with economic security in job provisions and upyick startup tech industry. Result also submits that intelligence sharing of players domicile in the security architecture alongside private security industry positively influences public safety which could reinforces the Global safe school projects and slow down the widening illiteracy trajectories. The study recommends that government should establish fusion centres for all actors particularly, private security industry and NSCDC, as it will consolidate nation's economic security further. Study also recommends that while private security could assist in the Safe school projects, NSCDC should provide the needed horizon security which ensures public safety.

Keywords: Intelligence Community; Participatory Theory; Private Security Industry; Security Architecture

1. Introduction

Global and local insecurities routinely inform and interact with each other; hence, the acceptance that security measures designed to prevent and manage international threats, demands local intelligence sharing networks from remote to metropolitan settings. Impact from the proliferation of Private Guard Companies (PGC) in Nigeria under the regulations of Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC) is not yet seen nor felt on the reduction of crime and criminalities in the country, Nigeria. The constricted operational landscape within which private security firms operate, could be seen in their inability to compete favourably in job security provision nor public safety delivery, compared to their counterparts in developed clime, whose operational spreads could be felt across the globe.

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There are an estimated 20 million private security workers worldwide while the industry is worth approximately \$180 billion, expected to grow beyond the GDP of 100 countries including Portugal, Romania and Hungary. Evidence abound that half of the planet's population lives in countries where there are more private security workers than police officers. India has an estimated 7million private guards as against 1.4million police officers, similarly there are 5 million people employed in private security compared to a police strength of 2.7 million in China while there are over 1.1 million private security guards in the U.S. compared to 666,000 police officers (McCarthy, 2017). In Nigeria, the manpower strength of both Nigeria Police and NSCDC is below 550,000 compared to over 1.2million private guards (Mungadi & Onibiyo, 2020).

According to IBIS (2022), there are 11,604 Security Services businesses in the US as of 2022, whether they're patrolling shopping malls, conducting screening at airports or protecting VIPs, private security guards have become an increasingly common sight across the world. In many countries, they are armed with handguns and even dress in uniforms similar to the police. The soaring demand has bode well for companies like G4S, the world's largest private security firm, which boasts of 585,000 employees and revenues of nearly \$10 billion (McCarthy, 2017) While Nigeria is not insulated from the preponderance of private security services, there is a long established disconnects between private security companies and the mainstream of internal security, as virtually all government security agencies could be seen competing with private guard companies. The NSCDC, are mandated by law to regulate the activities of PSCs in Nigeria but they are indicted to struggle with PGC over job contracts (Igbo & Chinwokwu, 2020; Gucia & Manning, 2007).

Bouwhuis (2018) submitted that tasks which are traditionally performed by public law enforcement agencies are being outsourced to private security companies due to rise in new threats level from non-state actors ranging from international terrorism, religious extremism, radicalism. The liberalists view of the provision of security that, the pursuance of security can be achieved with the involvement of other actors offering the same services (Mutonyi et al.2020). Still, it must be kept in mind that private security involvement in the public domain is a very complex subject which can be looked at from many different angles. Nonetheless, it is possible to confirm certain relations such that the foremost influencers on private security company involvement in the public domain are regulations and government attitude toward outsourcing traditional public law enforcement tasks. The recent outsourcing of the protection of national assets of oil pipelines, to private protection services of a reknown warlords Tompolo is a case in point that has seen Private security companies and Government Security Agencies jointly brainstorming on way forward and such is a step in the right direction for a responsive security architecture (Izuaka, 2022).

Interestingly, the expansive operations of private guard companies suffered some restraint from seeming lacuna in the enabling law of NSCDC act 2007, which did not exclude institutions from operating in house guard system, thus the ability of establishments to operate in house guard system could be seen as a leakage to the expansion of private guard business in Nigeria. Efforts by the NSCDC to seal corporate entities off, was restrained by a Federal High Court, which ruled that any person or corporate entity who employs more than one person to secure its private property must not necessarily engage the services of a private guard company, as canvassed by the NSCDC and Interior Minister (The Whistler, 2020; The Nation, 2020).

This background then call for review, of the extent insecurity is impacting the polity of the nation amidst untapped Intel abundance, as private guard companies who could be seen as an Early Warning Early Response mechanism (EWER) are cut off from the intelligence sharing network of Nigeria. Private Guards services could be properly situated as example of situational crime prevention strategy and the more this could be exemplified the more government security agencies can push mainstream crimes back rather been warehoused in individual houses of affluence ones thereby depriving the larger population from security provisions which should be seen as a social goods for all. Situational crime prevention aims to reduce the opportunity for crime through a pragmatic approach by altering opportunistic premises and modifying environmental factors to limit offenders from engaging in criminal behaviour. EWER mechanism seeks to harness the shared intelligence between communities, security actors, and government, in bids to identify and address imminent threats and to ensure civilian protection. It is not necessarily set up in conflict zones but deserves to be seen in national security architecture (Mungadi, 2021; Search for Common Ground, 2020).

Interestingly, all licensed Private Guard Companies officially falls under the purview of the NSCDC but there exist a vacuum as to any operational interface into NSCDC's EWER mechanisms. There is no framework that afford both regulator and the regulated, to deepen awareness and protection through intelligence sharing, no platform for the recognition of outstanding services by Guards, absence of employment slot extensions to private guards. Rather, the operational landscape is pervaded with superiority complex and unhealthy competition from federal force agencies, whereas elements of joint shows of force, could be all the needed links along with inter training platform to trigger the requisite synergy. In developed clime, private security officers have coercive powers similar to the police (Rushin, 2012).

The huge intelligence sharing networks disconnect between private security companies and public security agencies could be seen in skipped roles that are tied to intelligence sharing; observe and report and call for help in distress. There is virtually no platform for private security companies to observe and reports in their various beats locations knowing well that the military, Police, DSS and NSCDC are competing with them in man guard duty particularly in the oil and Gas business, telecommunications and banking sectors. The competition is so severe that most Private security companies are left in the cold when their clients are in distress.

Crime and violence in schools is a formidable concern and should not be taken lightly, many school are veering into crime-prevention strategies aimed at reducing crime and the fear of crime in the education sector which mirrors the larger society. Such security measures include partnering with local security stations, to officers, policies requiring translucent backpacks, the implementation of dress codes, and random searches of students' possessions and lockers, installing video cameras, utilizing weapon-detection systems; metal detectors, and blocking or restricting access to school facilities with entry-control devices of electronic key cards.

In efforts to achieve the objective of studies, answers will be provided for the following research questions:

- How does the intelligence community influences private guard company's services in Nigeria?
- What is the influence of the intelligence community on economic security provision by private guard company's services in Nigeria?
- To what extent does the intelligence community aggravate public safety services by private guard company's services in Nigeria?

While emphasis are much on the regulations of private guard companies to scale up their professionalism while networking between private guard companies with the security architecture is largely missing in reality except on the paper, and this weakens then criminal justice system which is a components of the nation's security architecture.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual Framework

2.1.1. Private Guard Companies

Private security companies also known as private Guard Companies in Nigeria, are firms that provide security services to clients in exchange for a fee, with limited jurisdiction only to the property owned by the client. Security is provided to protect the interests of the client, rather than the general public. The major difference between private and public sector security jobs is the employer. PGC are intricate part of office buildings, clubs & bars, streets, malls, & social events; weddings, political gatherings, concerts. The industry is currently regulated in accordance with the 'Private Guard Companies Act' of 1986. This Act mandates the licensing of all PGCs in Nigeria via a licensing authority. The Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC) is the licensing authority and derives its powers from the NSCDC Act No. 2 of 2003 and Amendment Act of 2007.

2.1.2. National Security Architecture

US has over 40 FS and its impact are seen in the national security architecture which is of human referent. The national security architectures which entail administration, decision-making, oversight structures and institutions, as well as national policies, strategies and plans (Bearne et al., 2005). A security template, the total criminal justice system which transmits the resilience, co-ordination and response rate of a nation to insecurity management (Mungadi et al., 2020). The security architecture of Nigeria has been grossly accused of being concentric and archaic (MaiBashira, 2022). The Nigeria National Security architecture is too unitary to respond to a complex federal structure like Nigeria (Yunusa et al. 2022). The Nigeria security architecture deemphasizes human security for State Security.

Collaboration mostly seen as reactive measures at the outbreak of ethno religious/communal clash, display of show of force as electoral process deterrence, or juicy counterinsurgency codenamed operation; Collaboration to remain a mirage without nationwide fusion centres (Mungadi et al. 2020). Abysmal failure of the national security architecture in achieving inter agency cooperation is seen in the incessant attack of correctional facilities by terror cells (Afuzie, 2022). This stresses the idea that security policies should capture all conditions that affect dignity, welfare, freedom of individuals and not only protect against war. It focuses on social and economic issues as they affect the individual, promoting the view that security is dependent upon human development and stability (Crawford, 2013; UNDP, 1994).

Human Security’s pillars cut across Economic, Education, Health, Community, Political, Environmental, and food security amongst others which should not be seen threaten.

2.1.3. Fusion Centres

A Surveillance-Industrial Complex” housing security agencies and corporate sector joined in mass Intel gathering, tracking and routine surveillance (Mungadi et al., 2022; German and Stanley, 2007). Established by states and LGAs to serve own law enforcement and emergency response needs. Sensitivities of federalism complicate this national architecture (Afuzie et al., 2022). A fusion centre is long overdue and jumpstarting it between the NSCDC and the Private Security companies will a step in the right direction, since collaboration not on papers if not coalesce into physical structure will remain an idea on papers hence the need for fusion centre (Mundai & Onibiyo, 2020)

Even as many federal officers are warehoused in the residence and corporate offices of VIPs, denying the public of the appropriate dosage of public officers for protections justified and entitled to by way of tax payment. Hence, the most direct question is the extent to which private security guards can take on at least some of the classic roles of ordinary police officers.

Table 1 Swot analysis of private security companies relevance in the security architecture

PGC swot analysis	
Strength	Weakness
Wider coverage in metropolis	Govt agencies rivalry
More critical assets under purview	High labour turnover
Access to techno deployment	Untrained labour
Intel from jurisdiction means emphasis	Complexity perception
Grey areas call for instant review	Poor remuneration
Opportunity	Threats
Foreign remittances	Loss of business
Global presence on stock exchanges	Bad press.
Big labour employer	Shareholder intervention
Government(s) patronages	High cost to operate
Moonlighting from public officers	Litigations
Government security agencies swot analysis	
Strength	Weakness
Federal supports	Officers’ superiority complex
Firearm bearing & logistics	Existing competition with pgc
Federal legislations backing	Boot trained against civility
Confirmation of intel points	Profit & service mismatch
Minimal crime response time	
Opportunity	Threats
Wider coverage in metropolis	Exit from needless rivalry
More cnaï under purview and firm grip assured	Trepidation on sharing intel with non public org
More estab more staff promo	Prosecution focused, fear of case compromise
More patches access of private CCTV	

Source: Mungadi and Onibiyo (2020)

2.2. Empirical Review

2.2.1. Intelligence Community, Private Guard Companies and Economic Security in Nigeria

Abrahamsen and Williams (2006) investigated the impact of bringing the private sector in security into the sector reform in Kenya and Sierra Leone, minding the extent to which people in developing countries have come to rely on private security providers for their day-to-day security needs. The study engaged explorative research design with reliance on secondary data and extant publications. Study submitted that 'bringing the private in' is crucial to a comprehensive understanding of the security situation in most countries and that any attempt to ensure better security for all must take account of private actors. Study was a cross country study, whose result cannot be generalized for Nigeria hence the need for this study using economic security and public safety to measure national security

Czop (2017) in a cross countries study, engaged qualitative research design to interrogate the de-monopolisation of security and development of private security companies in Poland and Europe. Study was exploratory in nature with reliance emplaced on secondary data and extant literature. Study opined that the most important fulcrum of private security sector development in Poland is its economic activities contributions. The study revealed that the threat level of terrorist signifies the need for greater involvement of security companies in providing security to facilities constituting the critical infrastructure of the state. Study though done in Poland and Europe deserves further interrogation beyond economic security which this study intends to capture.

Epps (2013) analysed the impact and roles of Private Security Companies in the Caribbean. The employed primary research method supplemented with surveys of PSCs, elite interview, newspaper articles, government documents, national legislation and regulations and relevant government regulatory agencies. Study opined that the private security industry has become a noteworthy source of employment in the Caribbean and is likely to remain for some time an influential player in the human and economic development of the region. Study though was done in the Caribbean on economic security, the to interrogate the economic security potential of the private security in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized

Klein and Hemmens (2018) examined the gamut of regulations emplaced on operations of private security companies in the United States, where the security guards outnumber police by almost 3 to 1. Study engaged triangulation method of research. Security guards perform many of the same functions as police officers and may even carry weapons, but to what extent do states regulate the private security industry. Study submitted that the economic importance of private security firms could be seen by the threshold of government regulations for employment in the security industry as requirement to provide adequate protection for the public. Study was done in the United States and the need for similar study in Nigeria cannot be ignored.

Liss (2014) examined the role of private security firms in Southeast Asia through practitioners vast menu of military and security services in the region that were formerly in the purview of government security agencies. Study employed qualitative research design. Study submitted that the contributions of private security companies on the employment front in the maritime sphere in South East Asia has made private firms become an essential part of the security sector and should therefore be integrated into state security reforms. Though study was done in South East Asia, the need to interrogate the economic security provisions of private Guards in Nigeria cannot be over emphasized

2.2.2. Intelligence Community, Private Guard Companies and Education Security in Nigeria

Shpeizer (2021) leveraged on the impact of global spread of neoliberalism on increase in practices of outsourcing and subcontracting schools protections to private security services in Israel for unique security climate. The study engaged qualitative research approach with semi-structured interviews, accompanied by observations and document analysis. Results emanating from study showed that the world of Israeli school security guards provide safety for schools as complimentary and in tandem with government security agencies. While study pointed out alienation of private guards and their ill treatment by employers this study captures economic security and public safety

Etor et al. (2020) employed descriptive statistics to examine provision of security facilities and security personnel service delivery in Universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study deployed quantitative research design on a population study of 440 security personnel while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Results from the study submitted that there is a significant impact between provision of security facilities and security personnel service delivery. The level of security service delivery in the Universities in Cross River State depend on the level of availability of security facilities for use by security personnel. Study was limited to Cross River and the need to query beyond education security by private security companies is further captured by this study

2.2.3. Intelligence Community, Private Guard Companies and Public Safety in Nigeria

Abrahamsen and Williams (2006) investigated the impact of bringing the private sector in security into the sector reform in Kenya and Sierra Leone, minding the extent to which people in developing countries have come to rely on private security providers for their day-to-day security needs. The study engaged explorative research design with reliance on secondary data and extant publications. Study submitted that the integration of private security companies into security reform goes beyond social and political orders maintenance but also in terms of who has access to security, and ultimately, for the legitimacy of

Ariel et al. (2017) leveraged on a randomized control trial in mass transit system to investigate the effect of private security agents in public spaces on crime in train stations in the South West of England. 30 private security guards for over 30 months were tasked to proactively patrol target locations, which were selected based on official crime records. Statistical analyses and findings suggested a significant 16% reduction in victim-generated crimes at the entire station complexes, with a 49% increase in police-generated detections at the target locations of 30% increase in drug arrests and 12% ticket fraud offences. The findings illustrate the efficacy of private policing for crime prevention theory. Study submitted that millions of formal surveillance agents in public settings are tasked to act as preventative guardians, as their high visibility presence is hypothesized to create a deterrent threat to potential offenders. Study though done in England was limited to public safety while this study extends to economic security and education security.

Bamidele et al. (2016) interrogated the contributions of private security companies to internal security in Nigeria. The study leveraged on convenience sampling technique in quantitative research design, data elicited from administration of 200 questionnaires on a total population of 1,775. Study established that private security companies immensely contributes to crime deterrence thus ensuring security in Nigeria. Study submitted that there is the need to strengthen the cooperation with government law enforcement agencies. Study was limited to community security while this study interrogates other intelligence community relationship with private security firms alongside contributions of economic security, public safety and education security by private security companies in Nigeria

Mutonyi et al. (2020) employed networks analysis theory to critically interrogate commercialized security industry's services on national security in Nairobi County of Kenya. The study took on a cross sectional survey design with the adult residents as the target population using multistage sampling technique was deployed on scheduled interviews, structured observation, and questionnaires to elicit data from respondents. Findings revealed that commercialized security though motivated by profit making plays a significant role that enhances state capacity in provision of security as well as contributes to safety of citizens. Study though done in Kenya focused on public safety while this study captures economic and school security

White et al. (2018) investigated the nexus between corporate interests and human rights abuse by private security companies in a fragile environment in Indonesia. The study employed qualitative research approach. Study submitted that There exists concerned human rights violations by private security personnel on indigenous peoples and other local inhabitants, who often find themselves entangled in protracted conflicts with multinational companies over access to their land in the logging and palm oil sectors in Sumatra reveal a pernicious and deliberate erosion and violation of rights of local inhabitants across the spectrum of security actors, showing that public security actors are protecting corporate interests rather than performing public functions.

2.3. Theoretical Framework

2.3.1. Participatory Theory

A participatory approach means that the person in charge of solving a problem or designing an innovation involves people who are directly concerned by the result of his or her work. Participatory theory is a vision or conceptual framework that attempts to bridge the subject-object distinction. The Thrust of Ferrer's (2002) participatory vision is to bridge the gap between the object subject distinctions. A turn from intra-subjective experiences to participatory events in our understanding of transpersonal and spiritual phenomena (Ferrer, 2002). Characterized by or involving participation especially providing the opportunity for individual participation participatory democracy participatory management (Merriam-Webster).

Instead of studying individual minds, the participation framework focuses on interaction, discourse and participation processes emerging between and among particular community members or communities in particular social and physical contexts (Lave & Wenger 1991). Same goes for participatory framework for all players in the intelligence community. Most of the metropolis in Nigeria are vastly covered and under the purview of the private Guard companies and the need to have a nexus at such level becomes vital.

The participatory theory in relation to Private Security Companies in Nigeria and Nigeria's National security architecture could be seen from the fostering and promotion of sense of belongingness for all Private Guard numbering millions in this impacted industry. This will also give purpose and sense of contribution to security, where there exist nodes of appreciation, employment slot opportunities to Man Guards, participatory of PGC will also scale up the use of new technology by these PGC who could swiftly adapt and develop new skills to enhance protection of their beats due to the acceptance and recognition accorded by NSCDC and the Ministry of interior. The rippling effect of these on an increasing social networks and social support will all culminated into frustrating crime and criminalities.

There is no gainsaying that the Nigeria's National security architecture is not participatory since major players that project civility are far away from the centre of the architecture while the architecture is not only militarized but concentric hence limited players are involved while the Nigeria Army whose operation nuances negates human security calls the shots in an over centralised security architecture. The trajectory differences immensely from what is obtainable in developed clime where human security drives the Homeland Security and nuances from all players in their various Fusion centres are seen playing out the protection of the country's security

The growth of private security services can be seen as a result of the privatization of public services previously provided by the state. Some school of thought posit that this growth, like that of other private services; private schools, private medicine, reflects the neoliberal tendency to convert political and public problems into market problems and to offer market solutions. Thus, in the neoliberal era, defense and security have become products, and the scope of the private security sector correspondingly expands (Brown, 2006; Meško et al., 2005).

3. Methodology

This study adopts exploratory research design; it tries to interrogate the impact of intelligence community and private guard companies on the National security architecture in Nigeria. The study measures impact on National security using constructs of education security, economic security and public safety measure as they relate to National security in Nigeria. Study engaged analysis of publicly available archive documents with reliance on secondary data. The research is conducted by examining literature concerning the private security companies, intelligence sharing, and national security in Nigeria. The literature was obtained through searches in publicly available material. Literature from non-serial publications, official reports, and conferences has been included particularly if they have been cited by other references in term of national security and intelligence sharing deficit.

4. Discussion

This study recognizes that all countries have legitimate security needs and that a security sector that is well tasked and managed served the interests of all. Resources spent on excessive procurement and perks for the military meant the denial of basic services to the poor and if Nigeria's counter narrative in militarization and counterinsurgencies operation is not yielding results in the face of excessive jailbreaks recorded in the countries (Afuzie, 2022), then there is the need to change the narrative of approach to good governance and bringing the private Guard companies on board the nation's security architecture will not only bring more jobs to the unemployed teeming populace but will afford security agencies in the mainstream (NSCDC and Nigeria Police) to focus on public safety than competing with private guards while stunting the growth of the sector

The review of literature reveals that there exist a weak link between intelligence, Private security and economic security in Nigeria. The rational for this finding could be the resultant effect of the non fusion of the private security sector into the national intelligence frameworks. The existence of competition by federal security agencies in manned guards and protection of critical national assets further constrict the ability of the private security to provide job opportunities for the teeming unemployed population thereby denying the unemployed apparent economic security. The finding is in tandem with the findings in the previous works of Klein and Hemmens (2018); Czop (2017); Epps (2013); Liss (2014); Abrahamsen and Williams (2006) who found connection between private security and employment generation.

The result gotten from empirical literature is that there is the presence of weak connection between private security companies and public safety. This could be explained by the concentric nature of national security architecture of Nigeria, which is more of military driven than of human security emphasis, leaving no space for the participation of the private security services despite their roles in commercial and private settings, an aggregate of public settings. The withdrawal of the Nigeria Police and the Nigeria security and Civil Defence Corps from corporate service protection to concentrate on public safety will go a long way. The presence of private security is enough deterrence while armed security agents should be seen at perimeter within a collaborative framework. This finding is consistent with the

findings in the previous work of Shpeizer (2021); Etor et al. (2020); Abrahamsen and Williams (2006); Ariel et al. (2017); Bamidele et al. (2016); Mutonyi et al. (2020); White et al. (2018) that had earlier submitted that private security companies in public safety could be improved upon.

5. Conclusions

The study concludes that incorporating the private security companies into national intelligence sharing networks have the potential to bring about increasing economic security as it will boost the confidence of security provision patronage as the awareness of the public will reflect on the collaborative relationship between the NSCDC, Nigeria Police and private guard companies as such seen relationship will open many economic fronts for private guards companies which will transmit to economic security for the teeming unemployed populations.

The study equally concludes that public safety and private guard companies could be further improved upon by government own security agencies tactically withdrawing from corporate protection services into the perimeter for horizon protection with arms operations backups. This will enthrone intelligence sharing network between private Guard companies and Nigeria security and civil Defence Corps. This simply means crime and criminality will have two strong layers to contends with; the private guard companies and the federal security agencies. Such collaboration sill transmit crime deterrence as against the present individual siloed arrangements.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made;

- The study recommends that the Federal Government should order the withdrawal of the Nigeria Police and Nigeria security and Civil Defence Corps from corporate Man guard services provision, a vacuum to be filled by the private guard companies.
- The need to see NSCDC and the private Guard companies they supervise, sharing intelligence through a mini fusion centre, cannot be over emphasized. The study therefore recommends that Federal, State and Local Government, particularly the ministry of interior should evolve fusion centres across the nation, for intelligence sharing amongst all security agencies including private guards companies as such will further ensure public safety.

Compliance with ethical standards

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